

METHODS OF THROWING THE BALL ON THE FOOT IN HANDBALL

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Handball is one of the most important sports for improving health and developing physical qualities. This sport has a multifaceted effect on the body, and during the game many different actions are performed: running, jumping, throwing the ball, etc. Students play this game with interest and curiosity, because the rules of the game are not so complicated. During the weight period of the game, each player takes an active and comprehensive participation. Fighting for the ball and striving for a good result make up the content of the game. Since handball is a team game, the players' movement is subordinate to the interests of the team. The game develops not only physical qualities, but also such qualities as consciousness, activity, discipline, purposefulness, behavior, restraint of emotions. In addition, the player develops such qualities as observation, attentiveness,

ABSTRACT

Handball is a team sport. Handball serves as a complementary way to practice other sports. Defensive player moves include carrying the ball, hitting back, blocking and catching the ball through the goalkeeper. It is very important that the goalkeeper never leaves the ball unattended and that the attacker determines in time how the ball is thrown before starting this movement.

creative thinking. Handball, like any other sport, is about scoring more goals and defending your own goal by following established rules. Each team will have seven players on the field (one goalkeeper and 6 field players). One team will have 12 players (10 players and 2 goalkeepers), including substitutes. If there are five players in the team, the game will begin. The game does not stop even if the player is sent off for any reason. Players do not replace the goalkeeper, but players can stand in place of the goalkeeper. The game lasts 2 halves of 15 minutes each (with a break between them for 10 minutes, the sides change places).

Handball can be played with any ball on different fields and even on street fields. It is enough to mark only the line of the field and the goal of 2x3 m. It is not so difficult: a 6-meter semicircle is drawn in front of the goal (from this point the ball is thrown into the

goal), and the middle line divides the field in half.

Standing, moving, stopping. In every sport, the player takes the starting position before performing any method. In handball, the most important thing is defense and attack. The position of the defender, goalkeeper and players is the same: legs are slightly open, knees are bent. The palms are extended forward, the toes are straight, and the arms are slightly bent at the elbows. This state allows the athlete to move freely, standing firmly, not only in defense, but also in attack. The attacker's arms are also bent at the elbows and stand at chest level. The legs are slightly bent, with one leg and shoulder in front. The foot width should not exceed 40-50 cm. The player can deceive the opponent, stop in order to choose a comfortable situation with his partner. The stop is carried out in two steps or in jumps. To do this, the legs are bent, the body is bent in the direction opposite to the direction of movement.

Catch the ball. The ball rests on one or two supports. To do this, arms are extended in the direction from which the ball is flying, palms and fingers are slightly turned down, and fingers are spread freely. When the ball gets close to the desired distance, it is immediately caught with the fingers.

Accurate and fast passing of the ball. This is the main method of interaction with partners, which allows you to successfully attack the opponent's goal. The transfer of the ball in tension depends on the degree of rotation of the body upon impact.

Carry the ball. The player can move the ball as much as he wants, move the ball as much as he wants, deceive the opponent. The ball can be carried once or repeatedly. When playing a one - shot ball, the player must walk three steps with the ball in hand and hit it on the ground in the fourth step, then walk three more steps to serve the

ball to his partner or hit the goal. However, when using a multipurpose ball, the ball can move across the entire field. This method came from the game of basketball. The ball is carried on the ground only when there is no opponent in front of the attacker.

This method is again used by opponents to return to the command area. When the ball hits the ground, the height of its jump should not exceed the waist.

Throwing the ball. The difference between throwing the ball and passing is that the ball is thrown with force from different positions (top, bottom, side, head, back). The ball is thrown from the ground in a seven-meter free kick, with a nine-meter free kick, unexpectedly from different distances. Throwing the ball while moving (from points 1, 2, 3) is not so difficult: when moving at high speed, the ball can be thrown without preparation with an arm bent at the elbow. In this position, the player moves the center of gravity on the leg to increase the power of the throw. In the basic position, there are several types of ball throwing. The speed of the ball is increased by supporting one or both feet. Running, swinging and throwing the ball in simple steps is done with one foot on the ground. The throw is made at waist level at an acute angle.

Throw the ball from the side. This technique is performed with the palm of the hand without bending the arm. There are the following techniques of possession, separation, hitting the ball:

- a) The possession of the ball thrown in one place depends on the position of the defender;
- b) Possession of the ball passed by the attacker in a jump;
- d) Jump after a corner kick performed by the attackers from a long distance;
- e) Taking the ball away from the forward standing in the first row. It depends

on the willingness of the defender and the position taken;

f) To deflect the ball when the opponent carries, passes or tries to hit the goal. It depends on how well the defender determines the direction of the ball and blocks its path with his hand;

g) Chasing an opponent and grabbing the ball. In this case, the defender blocks him from the front or from the side (he cannot touch the opponent's hand);

h) When a defender realizes that he is cheating by taking the ball away from an opponent who is trying to distract him, he may tackle the ball when the opponent kicks, hits the ground or passes it;

i) When the attacker throws the ball into the goal, the defensive player must stand slightly behind or to the side of the attacker so that he can clear the ball from the attacker's hand. The defender then jumps forward and upward at the same time as the offensive player and blocks the way the ball enters the goal with his paws.

Not only the goalkeeper, but also the defender is obliged to block the path of the ball thrown to the goal. In this case, the defensive player holds with both hands in the direction in which the ball can fly, and only the ball coming from the side can be blocked with one hand. The main methods of protecting the goal: jumping with raised arms, deflecting a flying ball to the sides and blocking with a foot, etc.

The ball flying from above is blocked on the ground with raised arms or to the sides. If the ball flies from above, it bounces and blocks its path with the palm of the hand. The claws should be spread apart to soften the ball. To block the path of a ball flying from the side at a height of 70-100 cm from the ground, the palm of the hand next to it is unclenched and both hands are placed in the direction of the ball.

To prevent the ball from flying 40-50 cm above the ground, the defender takes a step towards him and stretches his arms forward. If the ball goes over the defender's right or left side, if so, you need to tilt it forward a little. If the defender does not have time to block the ball flying very low, the method of blocking the ball with his foot is used. This method is prohibited by the rule, but it can be used in such cases. In this case, an attempt is made to extend the arm in the same direction as the foot. You can also sit down and block a ball that flies close to the ground or hits the ground.

Goalkeeper movement. The goalkeeper is the most important player on the team. He can hit most of the balls that hit the goal with his hand, some with his foot, and some with his body. In addition, the goalkeeper must also have the quality of speed. The goalkeeper must choose the right place in time to step on one or both feet when jumping with the ball. The goalkeeper also needs to know how to slow down as much as possible when returning the ball so that it is easier to get hold of the ball. The goalkeeper can hold a weak ball with two hands and a ball coming from the side with one hand. In addition to the above, there is also a way to block the ball from falling. This method is also used to catch the ball flying from the other side of the goal. Blocking the ball when it falls is carried out by swinging to the leg farther from it.

The opposition of the goalkeeper to the attacking opponent. In this case, the goalkeeper takes several steps forward towards the player who is carrying the ball from the main position. The goalkeeper's body leans forward, his fingers spread all the way. One leg opens 30-40 cm forward from the other. The goalkeeper throws the ball into play several times during the game. It can be lifting a partner a short distance or throwing

20-25m. Therefore, the goalkeeper should be well versed in the practice of positioning the ball or running. The collection of different special techniques used in the game to achieve a goal is the handball technique.

Today handball is a developing sport and the training of young handball players is of great importance. It is necessary to popularize and further develop handball, to form a healthy lifestyle among the population.

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